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Research Article

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF FLOATING TAPENTADOL HCL TABLETS

Mrs.T. Sowmya*, Dr.T.Mangilal, Thallam Sai Anjali, Mohammed Zaid Ul Arifeen,
Nuzhath Begum, K. Shiny Avenglin, A.Shyam Prakash
Smt.Sarojini Ramulamma College of Pharmacy, Seshadrinagar, Mahabubnagar-509001,
Telangana, India.

Abstract:

The oral route is the predominant and most preferable route for drug delivery, but drug absorption is unsatisfactory and highly variable in individuals despite excellent in vitro release patterns. Analgesics having similar effectiveness with improved compliance in comparison to opioids are valuable additions to the analgesic armamentarium. Polymers used in the drug delivery system are of two types Natural and Synthetic based on their origin. Both types of polymers have some advantages and disadvantages. This results in prolonged gastric retention time of floating forms which improve bioavailability of drug and improve clinical situations. FDDS is one amongst the GRDF's used to achieve prolonged gastric residence time. From the experimental results obtained, F4 formulation has been selected as the best formulation among all the other formulations. The in vitro drug dissolution studies from the formulation were found to be controlled release. All the evaluation parameters obtained from the best formulation were found to be satisfactory. Based on the observations, prepared tablets were analysed for various parameters like weight variation, hardness, thickness, friability, swelling and floating time, In-vitro drug release, extended to 10 hours, with formulation F4 demonstrating 83.9% drug release has been seen.

Key words: Tapentadol HCL, Gastric residence time, Floating tablets, Hydrochloride.

Corresponding author:**T.Sowmya,**

Smt.sarojini ramulamma college of pharmacy,
Seshadrinagar, Mahabubnagar-509001, Telangana, India.
E.Mail: sowmya092@gmail.com, Ph: 9052451820

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Oral administration is the most convenient and preferred means of any drug delivery to systemic circulation. Oral controlled release drug delivery has recently been of increasing interest in pharmaceutical field to achieve improved therapeutic advantages, such as ease of dosing administration, patient compliance and flexibility in formulation. Drugs that are easily absorbed from gastrointestinal tract (GIT) and have short half-lives are eliminated quickly from the systemic circulation. To avoid this limitation, the development of oral sustained-controlled release formulations is an attempt to release the drug slowly into the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) and maintain an effective drug concentration in the systemic circulation for a long time. After oral administration, such a drug delivery would be retained in the stomach and release the drug in a controlled manner, so that the drug could be supplied continuously to its absorption sites in the gastrointestinal tract (GIT) ¹. Prolonged gastric retention improves bioavailability, increases the duration of drug release, reduces drug waste, and improves the drug solubility that are less soluble in a high pH environment². Sustained release, sustained action, prolonged action, controlled release, extended action, timed release, depot and repository dosage forms are terms used to identify drug delivery systems that are designed to achieve a prolonged therapeutic effects by continuously releasing medication over an extended period of time after administration of a single dose. The term "controlled release" has become associated with those systems from which therapeutic agents may be automatically delivered at predefined rates over a long period of time. The safety margin of high-potency drugs can be increased, and the incidence of both local and systemic adverse side effects can be reduced in sensitive patients ³.

Gastrointestinal tract physiology

The stomach is situated in the left upper part of the abdominal cavity immediately under the diaphragm. Its size varies according to the amount of distension: up to 1500ml following a meal; after food has emptied, a collapsed state is obtained with resting volume of 25–50ml (Waugh & Grant, 2001). The stomach is anatomically divided into three parts: fundus, body, and antrum (or pylorus). The proximal stomach, made up of fundus and body regions, serves as a reservoir for the ingested materials, while the distal region (antrum) is the major site of mixing motions, acting as a pump to accomplish gastric emptying.

Gastrointestinal Motility

Two distinct patterns of gastrointestinal motility and secretion exist corresponding to the fasted and fed states. As a result, the bioavailability of orally administered drugs will vary depending on the state of feeding. In the fasted state, it is characterized by an inter-digestive series of electrical event and cycle, both through the stomach and small intestine every 2–3h. This activity is called the inter digestive myoelectric cycle or Migrating motor complex (MMC). MMC is often divided into four consecutive phases: basal (Phase I), pre-burst (Phase II), burst (Phase III), and Phase IV intervals.

Emptying of Dosage Form from The Stomach

To achieve gastric retention, the dosage form must resist premature gastric emptying. For this, the dosage form must be able to withstand in the stomach against the force caused by peristaltic waves. Furthermore, once its purpose has been served the dosage form should be removed from the body with ease. Table 1 explains the GIT transit time of various dosage forms [4,5,6].

Factors Affecting Gastric Retention⁶

Gastric residence time of an oral dosage form is affected by several factors. To pass through the pyloric valve into the small intestine the particle size should be in the range of 1 to 2 mm. The pH of the stomach in fasting state is ~1.5 to 2 and in fed state is 2 to 6. A large volume of water administered with an oral dosage form raises the pH of stomach contents to 6 to 9. Stomach doesn't get time to produce sufficient acid when the liquid empties the stomach; hence generally basic drugs have a better chance of dissolving in fed state than in a fasting state.

The gastric retention time (GRT) of dosage form is controlled by several factors, that affect their efficacy as a gastro retentive system.

- i. Density: Density of the dosage form should be less than the gastric contents (1.004gm/ml).
- ii. Size and Shape: Dosage form units with a diameter of more than 7.5 mm are reported to have an increased GRT compared to those with a diameter of 9.9 mm. The dosage form with a shape tetrahedron and ring shape devices with a flexural modulus of 48 and 22.5 kilopond per square inch (KSI) are reported to have better GIT for 90 to 100 % retention at 24 hours compared with other shapes.
- iii. Fed or Unfed State: Under fasting conditions, the GI motility is characterized by periods of strong motor activity or the migrating myoelectric complexes (MMC) that occur every 1.5 to 2 hours. The MMC sweeps undigested material from the

stomach and if the timing of administration of the formulation coincides with that of the MMC, the GRT of the unit can be expected to be very short. However, in the fed state, MMC is delayed and GRT is considerably longer.

iv. Nature of the meal: Feeding of indigestible polymers of fatty acid salts can change the motility pattern of the stomach to a fed state, thus decreasing the gastric emptying rate and prolonging the drug release.

v. Caloric Content: GRT can be increased by 4 to 10 hours with a meal that is high in proteins and fats.

vi. Frequency of feed: The GRT can increase by over 400 minutes when successive meals are given compared with a single meal due to the low frequency of MMC.

vii. Gender: Mean ambulatory GRT in meals (3.4 ± 0.4 hours) is less compared with their age and race-matched female counterparts (4.6 ± 1.2 hours), regardless of the weight, height and body surface.

viii. Age: Elderly people, especially those over 70 years, have a significantly longer GRT.

ix. Posture: GRT can be very between supine and upright ambulatory states of the patients

x. Concomitant drug administration: Anticholinergic like atropine and propantheline opiates like codeine and prokinetic agents like metoclopramide and Cisa pride.

Floating Drug Delivery System

Floating drug delivery systems (FDDS) or hydrodynamically controlled systems are low-density systems that have sufficient buoyancy to float over the gastric contents and remain buoyant in the stomach without affecting the gastric emptying rate for a prolonged period. While the system is floating on the gastric contents, the drug is released slowly at the desired rate from the system. After the release of drug, the residual system is emptied from the stomach. This results in an increased GRT and better control of the fluctuations in plasma drug concentration. However, besides a minimal gastric content needed to allow the proper achievement of the buoyancy retention principle, a minimal level of floating force (F) is also required to keep the dosage from reliably buoyant on the surface of the meal. Many buoyant systems have been developed based

on granules, powders, capsules, tablets, laminated films and hollow microspheres ⁷.

Classification of Floating Drug Delivery System ⁸

1. Single Unit Floating Dosage Systems

a) Effervescent Systems (Gas-generating Systems)

b) Non-effervescent Systems

2. Multiple Unit Floating Dosage Systems

a) Non-effervescent Systems

b) Effervescent Systems (Gas-generating Systems)

c) Hollow Microspheres

d) Raft Forming Systems.

Floating Mechanism

Effervescent floating system prepared with help of swellable polymers such as methyl cellulose, chitosan and various effervescent compounds eg: Sodium bicarbonate, Tartaric acid and citric acid. After oral administration this dosage in contact with the gastric content CO₂ liberate and gas entrapped in swollen hydrocolloids which provide buoyancy to the dosage form. Gas

Generating agent pushes the tablet towards the surface of gastric fluid, time required for this process is called log time. Then drug releases at surface of gastric fluid in controlled manner. Controlled release approximately 6-8 hrs. In targeted regions ⁹.

These effervescent systems are further classified into two types:

1) Gas generating systems.

2) Volatile liquid or Vacuum containing systems.¹⁰.

Drug Candidates suitable for floating Drug Delivery:

1. Drugs which shows site-specific absorption in the stomach or upper parts of the small

intestine. For example: furosemide, riboflavine-5-phosphate.

2. The drugs which are unstable in the lower part of GIT. For example: captopril.

3. Drugs required to exert local therapeutic action in the stomach. For example: antacids,

anti-H. pylori agents, misoprostol.

4. Drugs with variable bioavailability. For example: satolol HCl.

5. Drugs which are insoluble in intestinal fluids. For example: quinidine, diazepam

Effervescence

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Advantages of FDDS^{12,13}

The Floating systems are advantageous for drugs meant for local action in the stomach. e.g. antacids.

Acidic substances like aspirin cause irritation on the stomach wall when they come in contact with it. Hence FDDS may be useful for the administration of aspirin and other similar drugs.

The Floating systems are advantageous for drugs absorbed through the stomach. E.g. Ferrous salts, antacids.

Administration of prolong release floating dosage forms, tablets or capsules, will result in dissolution of the drug in the gastric fluid. They dissolve in the gastric fluid would be available for absorption in the small intestine after emptying of the stomach contents.

It is therefore expected that a drug will be fully absorbed from floating dosage forms if it remains in the solution form even at the alkaline pH of the intestine.

As sustained release systems, floating dosage forms offer various potential advantages. Drugs that have poor bioavailability because their absorption is

limited to upper GI tract can be delivered efficiently thereby maximizing their absorption and improving their absolute bioavailability.

Limitations of FDDS

Floating system is not feasible for those drugs that have solubility or stability problem in G.I. tract.

These systems require a high level of fluid in the stomach for drug delivery to float and work efficiently coat, water.

The drugs that are significantly absorbed through out gastrointestinal tract, which undergo significant first pass metabolism, are only desirable candidate.

The dosage form should be administered with a full glass of water (200-250 ml).

These systems do not offer significant advantages over the conventional dosage forms for drugs, which are absorbed throughout the gastrointestinal tract.

The drug substances that are unstable in the acidic environment of the stomach are not suitable candidates to be incorporated in the systems.

The aim of the present study is to formulate Floating tablets of Tapentadol HCL drug that is used to treat analgesia.

Materials

Tapentadol hydrochloride form –Aprocured From Sun Pharma Pvt Limited as Gift Sample, HPMC (polymer), Dextrose, Sodium carbonate, citric acid, PVP K30.Used In this Study.

Methods

Preparation of Tapentadol Hydrochloride Tablets

Four different formulations were prepared using various concentrations of the sodium bicarbonate and HPMC (polymer). The concentration of polymers for the factorial design was finalized based on the evaluation of trials. In preliminary study, sodium bicarbonate was used in concentration as a floating agent. citric acid is used in combination with sodium bicarbonate in all batches. HPMC (polymer)is a traditional pharmaceutical excipient with favorable safety profile. Used as a raw material for coatings with moderate strength, moderate moisture and oxygen barrier properties, elasticity. And it is also used as a tablet binder and as a tablet matrix for extended release. Pvp k30 has multiple uses including as a binder for tablets and capsules, and film former for ophthalmic solutions.

The tablet of trial batches was prepared by direct punching method. The tablet has been punched under the tablet punching machine.

General procedure for the Preparation

Weigh the following drug and the materials mentioned below, according to their quantities. By using motor and pestle Tapentadol Hydrochloride

(drug) and the excipients are grinding into fine powder. The powder is sieved to separate the particles of different sizes. The powder which is obtained is fine particles. According to the given quantity tablets are weighed and punched by 4 different formulations which vary in their polymer and binders.

Figure 1 Optimized formulation Granules

Table 1 Formulations of Tapentadol Hydrochloride

S.NO:	MATERIALS:	F1	F2	F3	F4
01.	Tapentadol Hydrochloride form A (DRUG)	100 mg	100mg	100mg	100mg
02.	HPMC (Polymer)	200mg	100mg	150mg	175mg
03.	Dextrose	66mg	216mg	116mg	141mg
04.	Na ₂ CO ₃	70mg	70mg	70mg	70mg
05.	Citric acid	10mg	10mg	10mg	10mg
06.	PVP K30	4mg	4mg	4mg	4mg

The formulated tablets were evaluated for the following Pre, post compression quality control studies and dissolution studies

Pre Compression studies

1. Angle of Repose: It is defined as the maximum angle possible between the surface of a pile of powder and the horizontal plane.

Angle of Repose of granules was determined by the funnel method. Accurately weighed powder blend was taken in the funnel. Height of the funnel was adjusted in such a way the tip of the funnel just

touched the apex of the powder blend. Powder blend was allowed to flow through the funnel freely on to the surface. Diameter of the powder cone was measured and angle of repose was calculated using the following equation¹⁴.

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} (h/r)$$

Where:

θ = angle of repose

h = height in cms

r = radius in cms

The angle of repose has been used to characterize the flow properties of solids. It is a characteristic related to inter particulate friction or resistance to movement between particles.

Table No 3: Angle of Repose Limits
Flow Properties and Corresponding Angles of Repose

Flow Property	Angle of Repose (degrees)
Excellent	25–30
Good	31–35
Fair—aid not needed	36–40
Passable—may hang up	41–45
Poor—must agitate, vibrate	46–55
Very poor	56–65
Very, very poor	>66

Density

a. Bulk density (BD): It is the ratio of total mass of powder to the bulk volume of powder. Weigh accurately 25 g of granules, which was previously passed through 22# sieve and transferred in 100 ml graduated cylinder. Carefully level the powder without compacting, and read the unsettled apparent volume. Calculate the apparent bulk density in gm/ml by the following formula¹⁸.

Bulk density = weight of powder/ Bulk volume.

$$BD = \frac{M}{V_0}$$

M = mass of the powder

V₀ = bulk volume of the powder.

b. Tapped density (TD): It is the ratio of total mass of powder to the tapped volume of powder. Weigh accurately 25 g of granules, which was previously passed through 22# sieve and transferred in 100 ml graduated cylinder of tap density tester which was operated for fixed number of taps until the powder bed volume has reached a minimum, thus was calculated by formula¹⁸.

Tapped density = Weigh of powder / Tapped volume

$$Dt = \frac{M}{V_f}$$

M = mass of the powder

V_f = tapped volume of the powder.

1. Carr's Index:

Compressibility index of the powder blend was determined by Carr's compressibility index. It is a simple test to evaluate the BD and TD of a powder and the rate at which it packed down¹⁹. The formula for Carr's index is as below:

$$\text{Compressibility index} = 100 \times \frac{\text{Tapped density} - \text{Bulk density}}{\text{Tapped density}}$$

2. Hausner's Ratio:

Hausner's Ratio is a number that is correlated to the flow ability of a powder¹⁹.

$$\text{Hausner's Ratio} = \frac{\text{Tapped Density}}{\text{Bulk Density}}$$

Table 2 Compressibility Index Limits
Scale of Flow ability (USP29-NF34)

Compressibility Index (%)	Flow Character	Hausner's Ratio
≤ 10	Excellent	1.00-1.11
11-15	Good	1.12-1.18
16-20	Fair	1.19-1.25
21-25	Passable	1.26-1.34
26-31	Poor	1.35-1.45
32-37	Very Poor	1.46-1.59
> 38	Very, very Poor	> 1.60

B) Post Compression studies:

Appearance

Appearance is the first most required quality for the acceptance of tablet. General elegance and its identity play a major role for the consumer acceptance. Acceptance of the appearance of batches of the tablet has been done based on the measurement of the following factors like size, color, shape, presence or absence of odor, taste etc.

Size and shape

Size and shape of a tablet has been determined by its thickness. Size and shape of table plays an important role in its patient compliance as the size of the tablet increases it is not much easier for its administration. Micrometer is the devise which is used to determine the thickness of a tablet. It can be acceptable if the batch falls within the ±5% of standard deviation.

Organoleptic properties

Color should be distributed uniformly without appearance of any signs of mottling. Colour of the tablet should be compared with the standard colour for comparison.

Uniformity of thickness

To determine the uniformity of thickness random selection of tablets has to be done from each and every batch and need to measure its thickness independently. If the thickness of any single tablet varies then that batch will not be dispatched into market

Hardness

Figure 2 Monsanto Hardness Tester

The ability of a tablet to withstand for mechanical shocks is known as hardness. Pfizer hardness tester is the instrument which is used to determine the hardness of tablet. It is expressed in kg/cm². Take three tablets from each batch and hardness should be determined and the selection of tabled should be done randomly. Then the mean and standard deviation values should be determined.

Friability

Figure 3 Friabilator

Roche friabilator is the equipment which is used for the determination of friability. It is expressed in percentage. Note down the initial weight of the tablets individually ($W_{initial}$). Tablets are placed in a plastic chamber which revolves at 25 rpm and they are subjected to fall from a height of 6 inches in the friabilator for about 100 revolutions. Then measure the weight of the tablet (W_{final}) and observe any weight difference before tablet and after the friabilator processing. Limits: loss in weight less than 0.5 to 1% of the initial weight of the tablet should be considered as acceptable limits. Percentage of friability is calculated as:

$$F = \frac{(W_{initial}) - (W_{final})}{(W_{initial})} \times 100$$

Weight variation test

Random selection of 20 tablets from each batch should be done and note down the weight of the tablet individually and check for any variation in its weight. According to US Pharmacopeias small variations in the weight is negligible and can be accepted. Below is the acceptable limit of percentage deviation in weight variation.

Floating lag time and floating time

In vitro buoyancy was determined by measuring floating lag time and duration of floating. The tablets were placed in a 250 mL glass beaker containing 0.1 N HCl. The time required for the tablet to rise to the surface and float was determined as floating lag time. The duration in which the tablet remains floating was determined as floating time.

Swelling index

Tablets' swelling index was measured in 0.1 N HCl. Tablets were weighed individually and given the W_0 label. They were then individually put into glass beakers with 100 ml of 0.1 N HCl at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The tablets were taken out of the beaker on a regular basis, and any extra surface water was wiped off with blotting paper before the pills were weighed again and recorded as W_t . Next, the swelling index was computed using the following formula.

$$\text{Swelling index} = \frac{(W_t - W_0)}{W_0} \times 100$$

Where, W_t = weight after swelling

W_0 = weight before swelling

Dissolution test

Figure 4

Dissolution test Apparatus

Dissolution rate of Tapentadol HCL tablets was studied using USP II (paddle Type) dissolution test apparatus. The quantity of dissolution medium was 900 ml of 0.1N HCL, with the speed of rotation at 100 rpm and the temperature was set at 37 ± 0.5 c. The sample was withdrawn at different time intervals. The withdrawn samples were suitably diluted with more quantity of dissolution medium and the same volume was replaced with fresh dissolution medium. The samples were then studied in UV spectrophotometer at 273 nm for Tapentadol content. The release rate at different time intervals were then determined.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Calibration curve of Tapentadol hydrochloride in 0.1N HCL

100mg of drug dissolved in 100ml distilled water. From this stock A Solution (1000 μ g/ml), 10ml is pipette out and is made up to 100ml (stock B) with 0.1N HCL. From stock B (100 μ g/ml) solution, 1ml is taken and is made up to 10ml (stock C). It gives 10 μ g/ml. From this solution aliquots of 2, 6, 10, 14, and 18 are transferred into series of 10ml volumetric flasks and the volume is made up to 10ml using 0.1N HCL. The absorbance of these solutions measured at 272nm by UV Spectrophotometer.

Table 3 Standardization of Tapentadol HCL

S.No	Concentration(μ g/ml)	Absorbance
1	2	0.154
2	4	0.281
3	6	0.428
4	8	0.560
5	10	0.703

Figure 5 Calibration curve

The unit formula for the formulation of Floating tablets Tapentadol hydrochloride was carried out. Trails F1, F2, F3, F4 were carried out. The pre compression parameters and post compression parameters of all the formulations.

Table 4 Preformulation studies

Formulation code/ Parameter	Bulk density	Tapped density	Angle of repose	Compressibility index	Hausners ratio
F1	0.50	0.625	28.17	20	1.25
F2	0.45	0.55	30.42	18.18	1.22
F3	0.53	0.62	29.24	16.120	1.19
F4	19.62	13.00	30.35	0.50	1.16

All the formulations were evaluated for various parameters such as Shape and size, Hardness, friability, Dissolution test, Drug content

Shape and Size

Shape is the form of an object or its external boundary, outline, or external surface, as opposed to other properties such as colour, texture or material type

Whereas, size is the measurement of other end, is the magnitude or dimensions of a thing. size can be measured as length, width, height, diameter, perimeter, area, volume or mass.

The thickness of all tablets was measured using a vernier calliper in cms

Hardness

Hardness is a method employed to measure the hardness of a material. Hardness refers to materials resistance to permanent indentation.

The hardness of the tablet was determined by using "Monsanto" hardness tester.

Friability

Friability testing is used to treat the durability of tablets during packing processes and transit. This involves repeatedly dropping a sample of tablets over a fixed time, using a rotating drum with a baffle.

In simple words, friability test tells how much mechanical stress tablets are able to withstand during their manufacturing, distribution and handling by the customer.

Floating lag time and floating time

In vitro buoyancy was determined by measuring floating lag time and duration of floating. The tablets were placed in a 250 mL glass beaker containing 0.1 N HCl. The time required for the tablet to rise to the surface and float was determined as floating lag time. The duration in which the tablet remains floating was determined as floating time.

Swelling index

Tablets' swelling index was measured in 0.1 N HCl. Tablets were weighed individually and given the W0 label. They were then individually put into glass beakers with 100 ml of 0.1 N HCl at 37±0.5°C. The tablets were taken out of the beaker on a regular basis, and any extra surface water was wiped off with blotting paper before the pills were weighed again and recorded as Wt. Next, the swelling index was computed using the following formula.

Table 5 swelling index

Formulation	Swelling Index (%) n=3	Floating lag time (sec) n=3	Total floating time (hr)
F1	63.5±1.9	64±2	9.0
F2	63.7±2.5	38±3	9.0
F3	69.9±2.1	45±2	12.0
F4	71.8±3.2	48±2	>12.0

Figure 6 Observing the prepared formulations to float

F

Figure 7 Best formulation (F4 batch tablets are floated)

Dissolution Test

Dissolution is the process by which solid substance enters into a liquid known as dissolution medium or solvent to form a solution.

Dissolution is a test which is used for a pharmaceutical product to evaluate the rate of release of a drug substance from the dosage form.

Table 7 Dissolution of Tapentadol HCL floating tablets

Time in hours	F1	F2	F3	F4
2	41.5±2.1	27.9±2.7	29.5±2.4	32.8±2.9
4	53.9±2.5	43.2±2.4	45.9±2.9	47.2±2.3
8	67.9±2.9	57.3±2.0	59.7±2.4	61.7±2.9
10	93.4±1.9	79.6±2.1	82.2±1.5	83.9±1.5

CONCLUSION:

Finally, it is concluded that Floating tablets of Tapentadol HCL, a central acting oral analgesic approved by US FDA for the treatment of moderate to severe acute pain were successfully formulated by employing direct compression method.

- Preformulation studies of Tapentadol HCL were performed.
- Evaluation parameters like size and shape, thickness, hardness, friability, swelling, floating time and dissolution studies was done for all the formulations.
- The *in-vitro* dissolution study showed 83.9 % of drug release at the end of 10 hrs from the formulation (F4).
- Further detailed investigation is required to establish bioavailability studies and efficacy including pre-clinical studies and clinical studies of these tablets.

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